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MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR ENHANCING PASSIVE INDOOR THERMAL AND VISUAL COMFORT IN DOUBLE-BANKED OFFICE BUILDINGS IN THE TEMPERATE DRY CLIMATE OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Many researchers have differed on the optimum values of Passive Indoor Thermal and Visual Comfort (PITVC) determinants for double-banked office buildings in tropical climates. The study is aimed at developing a mathematical model for enhancing PITVC in double-banked midrise office buildings, during the activity period (8 am to 5 pm), in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. It was achieved by evaluating the effects of Orientation, WWR, R-values, and shading devices on PITVC. A quantitative research design using an explorative design approach was employed in the study as well as an experimental research strategy through simulation method to enhance PITVC. The study used Bank of Industry building as a prototype of a double-banked office building. The Google Sketch-Up 2022 and OpenStudio simulation tools were used to evaluate the prototype building from January to December 2023. The data generated was analyzed using relevant statistical tools (MANOVA, ANOVA, column charts, graphs, and tables). The findings revealed that the best WWR for visual and thermal comfort are 45% and 15% respectively while the compromise value was 45%. the best values of projection factors for visual and thermal comfort are 0.35 and 0.6 respectively while the compromise value was 0.5. It was also noted that the R-value of external wall insulation material does not affect the visual comfort of an office building but affects operative temperature as well as relative humidity as the optimum value was found to be 3.61 m²·K/W. The mathematical model was developed as $A = -47.22 + 174.22WWR - 85PF + 6.33R \dots \dots 1$ Where A is orientation, WWR window-to-wall ratio, PF projection factor, and R is the R-value of the external wall materials.

Keywords: Daylight autonomy, Double-banked office building, Operative temperature, Thermal comfort, Visual comfort.

Introduction

There are many studies concerning passive indoor thermal and visual comfort in across the globe but little have considered building layout. A study conducted by Tereci et al. (2013) has revealed that there is significant impact of building typology on building energy performances. Other studies such as that of Musa (2023) Astrich, Morris, and Walters (2010) and Samir, Nouredine and Abdelhalim (2017) confirmed Tereci et al. (2013) findings. There are various ways of classifying office buildings in architecture, which include: classification based on form; circulation pattern; accessibility; building layout; and so, on as shown in Figure 2.1.

Figure 2. 1. Classification of office buildings

Source: Musa (2022)

Many studies in the tropics were able to predict PITVC but of conflicting values due to the failure to consider building spatial layout. For example: Mahmoud et al., (2015) and Hakim, et al, (2021) findings were not tie to any building classification while that of Salem et al., (2022) did not consider a number of variables such as WWR, R-values of the materials as well as building layout. Moreover, a study by Zhang, and Ji, (2022) have added a concept of energy without considering the building spatial layout.

Achieving the acceptable passive indoor environmental comfort, in office buildings is very important to the success of a sustainable office building. It is very vital to take passive thermal and visual comfort into account in their interactions in tropical nations like Nigeria to prevent environmental pandemonium. The study has shown that most of the mid-rise office buildings in Temperate dry climate in developing countries are of double-banked layout. For example, Prasetya, et al., (2023) noted that, most of the mid- and high-rise buildings in Indonesia are double-loaded corridor. Hassan, (2022) has noted that, double loaded corridor buildings have rooms accessed from both sides of the corridor and are more suitable for high-rise buildings due to their structural requirements. Another advantage of double-banked office buildings is in terms of economy of space and structural requirements. The study aims at developing a Framework for passive indoor thermal and visual comfort (PITVC) in double-banked office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. This was done by investigating the effects of window-to-wall ratio (WWR), Orientation, Overhang Projection Factor, and R-values of the exterior wall component of double-banked office buildings on PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. These brought about the following research questions:

- i. to what extent does the orientation (azimuth) affect PITVC of double-banked office buildings?
- ii. to what extent does the WWR affect PITVC of double-banked office buildings?
- iii. to what extent does the shading device affect the PITVC of double-banked office buildings?
- iv. to what extent do the R-values of the exterior wall component affect the PITVC of double-banked office buildings?

They brought about the following hypothesis: (H₁) states that the mean effects of PITVC are significantly different for at least one of the Azimuths in a double-banked office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria; Hypothesis (H₂) states that the mean effects of PITVC are significantly different for at least one of the WWRs in a double-banked office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria; hypothesis (H₃) states that the mean effects of PITVC are significantly different for at least one of the Overhang Projection Factors in a double-banked office buildings in the temperate dry climate

of Nigeria; hypothesis (H4) states that the mean effects of PITVC are significantly different for at least one of the R-value of external wall materials in a double-banked office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

The climate type is a fundamental factor in optimizing Passive Indoor Thermal and Visual Comfort and based on the various historical periods, climate could be classified into two (2): classical and modern. According to Rohl (2015), the ancient Greeks used reasoning to categorise climate during the classical era. The creation and spread of weather recording equipment in the middle of the 19th century is credited with giving rise to modern climate classification. Although many different modern climate classifications have been developed, they may all be broadly divided into two categories: genetic climate classifications and empiric classifications (Rafferty, 2016; Ritter, 2019). The study has adopted the empiric climate classifications as widely adopted for all practical applications as concluded by Djamila, (2018). Most climate classifications that are based on human comfort have their origin in Atkinson's (1953) climate classification (Koenigsberger et al. 2013) as shown by Musa (2022). The study has adopted Mobolade and Pourvahidi's (2020) climate classification based on the fact that it factored temperature, relative humidity, mean radiant temperature, and wind velocity in its method of classification. It also considered the gradual transition from one climatic zone to another as shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2. Classification of the Nigerian climate Mobolade and Pourvahidi.

Source: Mobolade and Pourvahidi (2020).

A Framework is an intellectual arrangement that acts as a roadmap for building concepts that develop into something meaningful. There are generally two types of frameworks: - theoretical and conceptual framework. A theoretical framework is a structure that can hold a theory of research study (Kivunja, 2018) and is used to limit the scope of the relevant data by focusing on specific variables. Ravitch and Riggan, (2017) noted that conceptual framework is the entirety of the researcher's ideas regarding the research topic, the issue to be looked into, the questions to be asked, the literature to be reviewed, the theories to be applied, the methodology you will employ, the tools, procedures, and data analysis, the interpretation of the findings, recommendations, and conclusions. Thus, it includes a theoretical framework in addition to other things. Another sub-frame classification is the optimisation framework which was defined by Ansari (2020) as the optimum technology that treats each waste type into useful products. The word "Optimisation" in this research simply means to make the indoor environment of the office buildings as comfortable as it can be in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria. Sukreet and Kensek, (2014) outlined four (4) different types of optimisation in architectural education, which include: parametric analysis; genetic algorithms; multi-objective optimisation; and passive optimisation

techniques. Passive optimization is the process by which an expert designer generates a large number of design possibilities, typically with the use of simulation software, to meet optimisation standards. Sukreet and Kensek (2014) have critiqued the process of developing three or more building options, comparing them cognitively to past experiences, and then using intuition to choose the best one. Coello, (2005) observed that multi-objective algorithm is more traditionally associated with engineering and scientific fields. Parametric analysis is the process of changing the values of a particular variable until a maximum or minimum result is obtained which indicates the best solution. The research has adopted the parametric method of optimization for achieving the study goal.

3.0 Methodology

An experimental research strategy using the simulation method was employed through an exploratory design approach and quantitative research design. A non-convenience probability sampling technique was used in selecting the Bank of Industry building as a case of a double-banked office building as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Iterative Prototype of Bank of Industry

The Iterative prototype of the Bank of Industry in Nigeria was modeled in Google Sketch Up 2022 and simulated in OpenStudio from January to December 2023 on the hypothetical sites devoid of surrounding buildings and trees, in Jalingo, Abuja, and Kaduna, using the various range of values of WWR, Azimuths, Overhang Projection factor, and R-values and their corresponding mean values of Daylight Autonomy (DA), Useful Daylight Illuminance ($UDI_{100-3000}$), Spatial Daylight Autonomy (sDA), Operative Temperature (OT), and Relative Humidity (RH) was recorded. Data generated were then analyzed using the MANOVA statistical tool with a significance value of 0.05, bar charts, graphs, and tables. Regression analysis was then used to establish the relationship between the four variables in a double-banked office building for PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

4.0 Findings and Discussion

The results are presented based on the following research questions:

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4.1. To what extent does the azimuth angle affect PITVC of double-banked midrise office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria?

The simulations were done with a double-banked office building with WWR of 8.8%, and R-value of 2.08 m²K/W. The results were presented in Tables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

Table 4.1. Simulation results of the effects of orientation on DA, sD, and UDI in double-banked mid-rise office buildings, in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Azimuth	0 ⁰	11.5 ⁰	22.5 ⁰	45 ⁰	67.5 ⁰	90 ⁰
DA	73	73	73	75	76	76
sDA	97.5	97.4	97.4	97.7	97.5	97.5
UDI	81	80	79	74	69	67

Source: Author, (2024)

It was noted that three out of eleven conditions have fulfilled the benchmarks as put forward by Illuminating Engineering Society (IES, 2022) which recommended a DA of 60% of the work plane illuminance; UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ of 80%, and sDA of 75% in office space. It has also been observed that, as the azimuth angle increases the DA increases but UDI decreases. When the daylight indicators were ranked, it showed that a building oriented at zero degrees has the best visual comfort as shown in Table 4.2. The finding is in agreement with the Anumah and Anuma (2007).

Table 4.2 Ranking of the daylight comfort metrics on building orientation

Azimuth	DA	SDA	UDI	Daylight Comfort	Remark
0	3 rd	2 nd	1 st	1 st	0 ⁰ is the best orientation to achieve Visual comfort
11.5	3 rd	3 rd	2 nd	2 nd	
22.5	3 rd	3 rd	3 rd	4 th	
45	2 nd	1 st	5 th	6 th	
67.5	1 st	2 nd	6 th	8 th	
90	1 st	2 nd	7 th	9 th	
112.5	1 st	8 th	6 th	11 th	
135	2 nd	4 th	5 th	7 th	
157.5	3 rd	5 th	3 rd	5 th	
180	3 rd	6 th	1 st	3 rd	
270	4 th	7 th	4 th	10 th	

Source: Author,

The simulation results of the effects of building orientation on operative temperature and relative humidity are presented in Table 4.3. The result showed that 11.5⁰ azimuth is the most appropriate orientation for better operative temperature and relative humidity. When values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together as indicated in Table 4.4, 11.5⁰ was found to be the most appropriate for PITVC due to the direction of air circulation at 45⁰ as observed by Bhatia, (nd) and Szokolay (2008).

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Table 4.3. Ranking of the orientation for PITVC

Azimuth	DA	SDA	UDI	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
0	3 rd	2 nd	1 st	1 st	2 nd	1 st	11.5 ⁰ is the most appropriate due to the effects of wind direction in the tropics.
11.5	3 rd	3 rd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	1 st	
22.5	3 rd	3 rd	3 rd	4 th	3 rd	2 nd	
45	2 nd	1 st	5 th	6 th	4 th	3 rd	
67.5	1 st	2 nd	6 th	8 th	5 th	4 th	
90	1 st	2 nd	7 th	9 th	6 th	5 th	
112.5	1 st	8 th	6 th	11 th			
135	2 nd	4 th	5 th	7 th			
157.5	3 rd	5 th	3 rd	5 th			
180	3 rd	6 th	1 st	3 rd			
270	4 th	7 th	4 th	10 th			

Source: Author, (2024)

4.1.1 Hypothesis Testing: -

a) H_{01} : There is no significant difference in PITVC among the midrise office buildings with different azimuth angles in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

One-way MANOVA was used to test if the effect of azimuth angle differs from one another significantly in one or more of the PITVC variables and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(25, 210) = 3.640$, $p < .00001$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 1.512$, partial $\eta^2 = .302$. Hence since there were more than two (2) levels of the independent variable, post-hoc should be conducted. A series of one-way ANOVAs on each of the PITVC variables was conducted as a follow-up test to the MANOVA. The results turned out to be statistically significant in all the five PITVC variables: DA ($F(5, 42) = 14.645$; $p < .000$; partial $\eta^2 = .635$), UDI ($F(5, 42) = 419.750$; $p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .980$), sDA ($F(5, 42) = 3.267$; $p < .014$; partial $\eta^2 = .280$), mean annual operative temperature ($F(5, 42) = 10.776$; $p < .000$; partial $\eta^2 = .562$), and mean annual relative humidity ($F(5, 42) = 2.857$; $p < .026$; partial $\eta^2 = .254$).

A series of post-hoc analyses using Fisher's LSD was conducted to examine individual mean differences comparison across the azimuth angles and PITVC variables. The result revealed that: except for azimuth 45, all DA were statistically significant with one another for all values that were greater than 22.5 but less than 45; except for the relationship between azimuth 0 and 11.5, all UDI values were statistically significant to one another; and finally, except for the relationship between azimuth 22.5 and 45, 67.5 and 90, all sDA values were not statistically significant to one another. That means all azimuth angles that are within 45 are not statistically significant to one another, while those that are not within the same 45 are statistically significant to one another. For example, 0, 11.5, and 22.5 are not significant to one another, while they are significant with 45, 67.5, and 90. The reverse is also true. For the relative humidity, it shows that, except azimuth 90 which was statistically significant to all others, all the average annual relative humidity were not statistically significant to one another.

4.2 To what extent does the WWR affect PITVC in double-banked midrise office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria?

The simulations of a double-banked office building, with an R-value of 2.08 m²K/W and a constant Azimuth angle of 11.5⁰ were done and the results are presented in Tables 4.4 and 4.5.

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Table 4.4. Simulation results for the effects of WWR on DA, sDA and UDI in a mid-rise office building, in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

WWR	0.15	0.2	0.24	0.3	0.40	0.425	0.45
DA	19	27	33	42	57	60	63
UDI	59	68	70	70	70	70	70
sDA	32.8	40.89	55.75	71.05	77.45	83.15	83.9

Source: Author, (2024)

Table 4.4 shows that none of the seven conditions fulfilled the benchmarks as put forward by Illuminating Engineering Society (IES, 2012) and Architectural Energy Corporation (AEC, 2013), which recommended a DA of 60% of the work plane illuminance; UDI₁₀₀₋₃₀₀₀ of 80% and sDA of 75% in office space. The most appropriate WWR for visual comfort was found to be 0.45 as shown in Table 4.40 which is contrary to the 2012 International Energy Conservation Code (2012 IECC) which recommended a different value of 30% (Makela, Williamson & Makela, 2011).

The simulation results of the effects of WWR on operative temperature and relative humidity are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 showing the effects of WWR for minimum Operative temperature and Relative humidity in a double-banked office building

The results show that, while relative humidity has met the condition recommended by ASHRAE Standard 55 (2013), none of the operative temperature met with the ANSI/ASHRAE Standard 55, (2013) It also indicates that 15% was the most appropriate WWR for better operative temperature as well as relative humidity as indicated in Figure 3. When the values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together as indicated in Table 4.5, 45% WWR was found to be the most appropriate for PITVC.

Table 4.5. Ranking of the WWR for PITVC in double-banked office buildings

WWR	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
15	7 th	3 rd	7 th	7 th	1 st	3 rd	45% is the most appropriate WWR for PITVC.
20	6 th	2 nd	6 th	6 th	3 rd	4 th	
24	5 th	1 st	5 th	5 th	3 rd	3 rd	
40	3 rd	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	3 rd	2 nd	
45	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	2 nd	1 st	

Source: Author, 2024

4.2.1 Hypothesis Testing: -

The one-way MANOVA was used to test if the midrise office buildings with different WWR differ from each other significantly in one or more PITVC variables. The homogeneity of variance-covariance matrices was tested using Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices and the Box' M valued obtained was 329.073 with a p-value of .000. Therefore the covariance matrices of the dependent variables were equal across groups for MANOVA. It was then tested and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(20, 296) = 18.828$, $p < .0000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = 2.240$, partial $\eta^2 = .560$.

A homogeneity for variance assumptions was tested for all the five PITVC variables before conducting a series of tests between the subject effects. Based on a series of Levene's F test, it was considered satisfactorily. A Series of one-way ANOVA's on each of the PITVC variables was conducted as a follow up test to the MANOVA. The results turn out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(4, 75) = 319.351$; $p < .000$; partial $\eta^2 = .945$), UDI ($F(4, 75) = 25.073$; $p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .572$), sDA ($F(4, 75) = 330.158$; $p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .905$), OT ($F(4, 75) = 5.1761$; $p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .235$) and RH ($F(4, 75) = 5.413$; $p < .0000$; partial $\eta^2 = .224$). A series of post-hoc analysis using Fisher's LSD were performed to examine individual mean differences comparison across all the five (5) different WWR and five PITVC variables. The result revealed that, all the five (5) WWR were statistically significant with one another.

4.3 To what extent does the shading device affect the PITVC of midrise office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria?

The simulations of a double-banked office building, with an R-value of $2.08 \text{ m}^2\text{K/W}$, azimuth angle of 11.5° , a Shade offset value of 0.3, and WWR of 45%, were done and the results are presented in Table 4.6 and Figure 4.

Table 4.6. Simulation results for the effects of projection factors on visual comfort of double-bank mid-rise office building in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Projection factor	0.35	0.400	0.450	0.500
DA	65	61	61	59
UDI	72	73	74	75
SDA	78.85	83.2	83	82.55

The finding has shown that the optimum projection factor for visual comfort in double-banked midrise office buildings in the temperate dry climate is 0.4, followed by 0.45, then 0.5, and lastly the 0.35 as indicated in Table 4.6.

The simulation results of the effects of the projection factor on thermal comfort are presented in Figure 4. The results have shown that, there was an annual average decrease in operative temperature of 1.58°C (5%) and an increase in relative humidity of 11.55% (26%) respectively between buildings with projection factors of 0.5 and that with no shading device in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Figure 4.6. Projection factor for minimum operative temperature and relative humidity in a double-banked office building

Source: Author, 2022

The result has also shown that 0.6 was the most appropriate projection factor for better operative temperature as well as relative humidity as indicated in Figure 4.6. When the values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together as indicated in Table 4.7, 0.5 projection factor was found to be the most appropriate for PITVC.

Table 4.7. Ranking of the projection factor for PITVC

Projection factors	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
0.35	1 st	3 rd	1 st	1 st	4 th	4 th	0.5 is the most appropriate P.F for PITVC.
0.45	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	3 rd	3 rd	
0.5	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	
0.6	3 rd	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	1 st	1 st	

Source: Author, (2024)

4.3.1 Hypothesis Testing: -

H_{03} : There is no significant difference in PITVC between double-banked midrise office buildings with different Projection factors of shading devices in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

The MANOVA test was conducted to test if there would be one or more differences between PF and PITVC variables and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(15, 222) = 5.479, p < .000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = .811$, partial $\eta^2 = .270$. A homogeneity for variance assumptions was tested for all the five PITVC variables before conducting a series of tests between the subject effects. Based on a series of Levene's F test, it was considered satisfactorily. A Series of one-way ANOVA's on each of the five PITVC variables was conducted as a follow up test to the MANOVA. The results turned out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(3, 76) = .863; p = .464; partial \eta^2 = .033$), UDI ($F(3, 76) = 5.274; p = .002; partial \eta^2 = .172$), sDA ($F(3, 76) = 7.35; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .225$), Operative temperature ($F(3, 76) = 14.425; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .363$) and Relative humidity ($F(3, 76) = 35.859; p < .000; partial \eta^2 = .589$).

4.4 To what extent do the R-values of the exterior wall insulation material affect PITVC of double-banked midrise office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria?

The simulations of a double-banked office building, with an azimuth angle of 11.5° , a shade offset value of 0.3, an overhang projection factor of 0.5, and WW of 45% were done and the results are presented in Table 4.8

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Table 4. 81. Simulation Results for the effects of R-values of external wall insulation material on visual comfort in mid-rise office building in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

R-values of external walling materials (m ² ·K/W)	1.04	2.08	3.12	4.16
DA	60	60	60	60
UDI	75	75	75	75
sDA	82.55	82.55	82.55	82.55

Source: Author, (2022)

The results revealed that all the four (4) conditions were the same. Which means R-value of external wall insulation material does not affect the visual comfort of an office building as indicated in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9 Ranking of the DA, sDA, and UDI against the R-value of external wall insulation materials

R-value of the external wall (m ² ·K/W)	DA	RANK	UDI	RANK	SDA	RANK	DAYLIGHT RANK
1.04	60	1 st	75	1 st	82.55	1 st	1 st
2.08	60	1 st	75	1 st	82.55	1 st	1 st
3.12	60	1 st	75	1 st	82.55	1 st	1 st
4.16	60	1 st	75	1 st	82.55	1 st	1 st

Source: Author, (2022)

The simulation results for the effect of R-values of external wall insulation material on thermal comfort are presented in Tables 4.10 and 4.11

Table 4.10. Simulation result for the effects of the R-values of external wall materials on the operative temperature in a double-banked mid-rise office building in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

R-values of external walling materials (m ² ·K/W)	1.04	2.08	3.12	4.16
Office	Av. annual temp	Av. annual temp	Av. annual temp	Av. annual temp
102	31	30.3	30	29.36
202	30.6	29.9	30.2	29.56
302	30.7	30	30	29.36
402	30.7	30	29.9	29.26
502	31.2	30.5	29	28.36
602	31	30.3	29.1	28.46
702	30.7	30	28.2	27.56
802	30.7	30	28.5	27.86
Mean value	30.825	30.125	29.3625	28.7225

Source: Author, (2024)

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Table 4.11. Simulation results for the effects of R-values of external wall materials on the relative humidity in a double-banked mid-rise office buildings in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

R-values of external walling materials (m ² ·K/W)	1.04	2.08	3.12	4.16
Office	Average humidity	Average humidity	Average humidity	Average humidity
102	54.6	59	61.8	64
202	51.1	55.5	59.2	61.9
302	52	56.4	60.9	63.6
402	56	60.4	62.3	65
502	58	62.4	60.6	68
602	56	60.4	58	65.3
702	60	64.4	59.7	65.8
802	62	66.4	61.1	67
Mean value	56.2125	60.6125	60.45	65.075

Source: Author, (2022)

The results have shown that, as the R-value increases, the thermal comfort also increases. When the values of daylight metrics and thermal comfort indicators were ranked together and also correlated, $y = 4.3253x + 47.795$ and $y = -0.6798x + 31.526$ were obtained for relative humidity and operative temperature respectively, and 3.61 m²·K/W was found to be the optimum R-value for PITVC as indicated on Table 4.47.

Table 4.12. Ranking of the R-values for PITVC

R-Value of external Insulated wall material (m ² ·K/W)	DA	UDI	sDA	Daylight Comfort	Thermal Comfort	PITVC	Remark
1.04	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	3 rd	3 rd	
2.08	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	2 nd	2 nd	
3.12	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	3.61 is the most appropriate R-Value of the external wall
4.16	1 st	1 st	1 st	1 st	4 th	4 th	for PITVC in the temperate dry climate of Nigeria

Source: Author, 2022

The result conformed with that of ANSI/ASHRAE/IES Standard 90.1 (2007, and 2010 editions) which recommended a minimum range of R-value of 1.0 - 2.7(m²·K/W) for non-residential building but contrary to that of Energy Conservation Building Code (2017), which recommended the optimum R-value of 3.7(m²·K/W) as the optimum for non-residential buildings.

4.4.1 Hypothesis Testing: -

The homogeneity of variance-covariance matrices was tested using Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices **and** the Box' M valued obtained is 22.633 with a p-value of 1.0, which was interpreted as non-significant based on Huberty and Petosky's (2000) guidelines. Therefore the covariance matrices of the dependent variables were equal across groups for MANOVA. The one-way MANOVA was tested and a statistically significant difference was obtained, $F(15, 174) = 4.810$, $p < .000$; Pillai's $\Lambda = .879$, partial $\eta^2 = .293$.

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A homogeneity for variance assumption was tested for all the variables before conducting a series of tests between the subject effects. Based on a series of Levene's F test, it was considered satisfactorily. A Series of one-way ANOVA's on each of the variables was conducted as a follow up test to the MANOVA. The results turned out to be statistically significant in all the DA ($F(3, 60) = .000; p = 1.00; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .000$), UDI ($F(3, 60) = .000; p = 1.00; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .000$), sDA ($F(3, 60) = .000; p < 1.00; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .000$), Operative temperature ($F(3, 60) = 21.165; p < .000; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .514$), and Relative Humidity ($F(3, 60) = 18.227; p < .000; \text{partial } \eta^2 = .477$). It showed that, visual comfort has no effect on R-value of external wall materials, while R-value has effect on thermal comfort.

A series of post-hoc analysis using Fisher's LSD was performed to examine individual mean differences comparison across all the R-values and four thermal comfort variables. The result revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the relationship among all the four variables (1.08 m²·K/W, 2.08 m²·K/W, 3.12 m²·K/W, and 4.16 m²·K/W).

4.5 Mathematical Models

To develop a relationship between the enhanced PITVC determinants for double-banked office buildings in the temperate dry climatic zone of Nigeria.

The mathematical models are limited to office buildings with horizontal shading devices, for it is more effective than the vertical in the tropics as observed by Al-Tamimi and Fadzil. (2011); Kim et al. (2012); Palmero-Marrero and Oliveira (2010); and Seok-Hyun et al. (2017). The framework was used to obtain four more enhanced PITVC values in each type of office building as indicated in Table 4.13 for double-banked office buildings. It was used to carry out the multiple regression to investigate whether the enhanced values of WWR, projection factor, and R-value of external wall material, could significantly predict different enhanced azimuth angles for PITVC in double-banked office buildings in a temperate dry climate of Nigeria.

Table 4.13. Five (5) sets of enhanced values of PITVC in double-banked office buildings in a temperate dry climate.

S/NO	Azimuth	WWR	PF	R-value
1	11.5	0.45	0.5	3.61
2	22.5	0.55	0.55	3.26
3	35	0.4	0.085	3.12
4	45	0.4	0.2	6.24
5	12.5	0.45	0.47	3.35

Source: Fieldwork, (2024)

The results of the regression indicated that, the model explained 99.9% of the variance and that the model was a significant predictor of azimuths, $F(3,1) = 58,922.2, p = .003028$.

The WWR, projection factor (PF), and R-value of external wall materials (R) contributed significantly to the model ($B = 174.222, p=0.003659$), ($B = -85, p=0.002143$), and ($B = 6.334941, p=0.002952$), respectively.

Equation 4.1 was also used to develop the mathematical model from regression results as follows:

$$\text{Azimuth (A)} = - 47.2226 + (174.2227 \times \text{WWR}) + (-85.0007 \times \text{Projection Factor}) + (6.334941 \times \text{R-Value})$$

$$\mathbf{A = - 47.22 + 174.22WWR - 85PF + 6.33R \dots \dots 4.3}$$

SI Units: A= (°); R= (m²·K/W); C= (°); M₁= (°); M₂= (°); and M₃= (° W/m²·K).

4.6 Framework Validation

There are various ways of validating a model which include: an expert assessment validation and the examination of framework output for reasonableness under a variety of settings of the input parameters.

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4.6.1. Experts Assessment Validation

This is the assessment of the model/ framework by an expert or group of experts and makes a pronouncement based on their experience whether the model is valid or not. They usually used face validation, which according to Haladyna (1999) and DeVon *et al.* (2007) was used to evaluate the appearance of the framework/ model in terms of readability, consistency of style and formatting, and the clarity of the model. Based on this, the summary of the developed framework and validation questionnaire was sent to twenty-two (22) PITVC experts, and fourteen (14) came back. Their responses are tabulated as shown in Table 4.14.

Table 4.14. Experts' evaluation of the framework and model developed in this research.

Respondents	Relevance	Clarity	Internal Consistency	Readability	Total (%)
1	5	5	5	5	100
2	5	5	5	5	100
3	5	5	5	4	95
4	5	5	5	5	100
5	5	4	5	5	95
6	5	5	5	5	100
7	4	4	4	4	80
8	5	5	4	4	90
9	5	5	5	5	100
10	5	4	5	4	90
11	5	4	5	4	90
12	5	5	5	5	100
13	5	5	5	5	100
14	5	5	5	5	100
Mean value					88.9%

Source: Author. 2024

It therefore shows that the Mathematical model was satisfactorily based on experts assessment.

CONCLUSION

The study has concluded that the ideal orientation for a new building is 11.5° but also depends on the building's spatial layout, window-to-wall ratio, shading device, and type of building materials used. Architects and other building professionals should not use the values from different researchers directly, for many researchers have not considered building spatial layout when recommending PITVC determinants such as Kandar, et al., (2011) and Building Energy Efficiency Code (BEEC) for Nigeria (2017) who recommended WWR of 25% and 20% in the tropics respectively.

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